

Influence Of Movies On The Marriage System

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a conceptual study on how the marriage system in a society has been influenced by the movies; particularly in the societies of India and Nigeria; as they all copy the Western world in their nature of marriage and marital lives. The medium of films allows people to express themselves and their culture. It has evolved into a tool for navigating contemporary society and a way to study people's cultures and traditions. That is to say, a society that values watching movies as a tool to learn new things or as a window into the outside world would always associate the lessons they learned with their cultural heritage. However, a theory of dramaturgy postulated by Erving Goffman has been adopted for a clear understanding of the topic of research. Goffman suggests that society is similar to a stage in a theatre. People react or act in much the same way as on-stage performers. In other words, people watch actors in films to learn how to act. It appears that practically every marriage contains a movie-like aspect. Despite this, Goffman had a strong commitment to his work on Impression management; and it refers to the actors' desire to impress their audience by acting in a manner that satisfies them. This is comparable to what is going on in modern society, where people frequently act, speak, dress, and behave similarly to actors. An Indian girl might, for instance, wear a miniskirt and speak fluent English to be perceived or addressed as European or American. Similar to Nigerian girls they wears Indian saris, necklaces, and cosmetics only to gain social acceptance and appear Indian.

I Introduction:

Movies in their existence are the avenue for people to express themselves and their society. It has become a mirror to navigate modern society, and a map to examine people's culture and tradition. In 1914, film industries were established in some European countries such as France, and Russia with the aim of storytelling and narrative on the culture and pattern of the society of European countries. The major aim was to tell the world about their way of life (Science Media Museum, 2020).

However, through effective movies nations make an effort to manage their reputations. Following Fullerton's model of the country concept, nations can interact with their foreign neighbors through a variety of integrants, such as cultural exports, tourism and tourism promotion, brand exports, governance/policy, people, and investment/immigration. Among these important platforms, movies are thought to be potent cultural exports that shape perceptions in other countries. It is a well-known truth in the tourism sector that movies play a significant role in inspiring people to visit abroad. For instance, the New Zealand island nation saw an increase in tourists after The Lord of the Rings trilogy was filmed there (Yang and Vanden, 2017).

As a result, practically every civilization and government intended to use films to inform people about their customs and culture, including marriage. For instance, Hindi and Nigerian films typically depict the nature of marriage, and love, and how affairs are conducted in these nations. According to Adorno and Horkheimer (1903–1969), who developed the concept of the "culture industry," people use media like movies to communicate to the outside world how their culture is practiced.

II How Movies Shaped The Contemporary Marriage System:

Every human society is based on the institution of marriage. It is the socialization and reproduction engine of the society. According to Salawu (2005), marriage is a universal

human institution that is not easy to define. This instructive reason, however, is that there is a great diversity in the system of marriage throughout the world. Therefore, as marriage is determined by the culture and life of the people, so also the culture of the movie determines the nature of the marriage. For instance, Albert Bandura (1971) asserts in his theory of social learning that a child's environment influences how they learn new things. That is to say, a society that values watching films as a tool to learn new things or as a window into the outside world would always associate the lessons they learned with their cultural heritage. These emerged in the societies of India and Nigeria, where 'some' cultures' marriage customs are influenced by films. For instance, a Nigerian bride-to-be who frequently watches Bollywood television might decide to look like an Indian actress for her wedding ceremony. Additionally, some Indian brides might believe that wearing a saree while she is being wed is a traditional practice that is outdated and retrograde. She would prefer to wear a white gown, as is customary in American films. Consequently, movies have influenced marital life itself. The way and manner in which the wife cooks food is learned from the movies nowadays. Wives living in Nigeria learned how to make Indian Roti, Aloo Paratha, Biryani, and the rest by watching Bollywood movies. Also in India, many American, British, and Chinese dishes in Indian homes were learned from watching movies.

However, parents in Nigeria gave birth to numerous children before the arrival of European films. Typically, they have 10 to 20 offspring during their lifetime. Thus, a Woman may also give birth to 3-6 children in India. But with the emergence of films and the westernization of culture, most now believe that having multiple children is foolish. Couples watched films where they learned about family planning and other procedures. Is a good notion for some people and a very edge of civilization for others.

III Relevance Of The Theory Of Dramaturgy On The Influence Of Movies On Marriage:

Dramaturgy is a sociological theory that was employed in the investigation of daily life and is a part of symbolic interactionism. Dramaturgy is an approach to explaining human behavior

that was developed by American sociologist Erving Goffman in his influential 1959 book *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life*. This theory holds that people behave in everyday life as though they are stage performers. Roles help to perform identity. In this context, the word "role" has two meanings: first, it refers to a theatrical character, and second, it describes how people fill roles in everyday life by playing various roles such as mother, friend, husband, etc. Dramaturgy contends that presenting oneself through a character is a strategy for participating in society (Libretex of Social Science, 2023).

Goffman is implying that society is similar to a stage in a theatre in this passage. People react or act in much the same way as on-stage performers. In other words, people watch actors in films to learn how to act. It appears that practically every marriage contains a movie-like aspect. From the wedding through the marriage itself, everything must be perfect. Despite this, Goffman nevertheless had a strong commitment to his work's impression management, as he called it. Here, impression management refers to how the actors behaved to please their audience because they intended to impress them. This is comparable to what is going on in modern society, when people frequently act, speak, dress, and behave similarly to actors. An Indian girl might, for instance, wear a miniskirt and speak fluent English to be perceived or addressed as European or American. Similar to Nigerian girls who dress in Indian attire and accessorize with jewelry and makeup to appear more Indian and win favor with the community. As a result, the role of films in understanding contemporary culture has become crucial (Ritzer, 2010).

More frequently still, we see Americans traveling with their families over the holidays. Indians weren't used to doing that before. Because of the movie, husbands frequently take their wives and kids to popular tourist destinations in India so they can take in the splendor of the natural world.

IV Conclusion:

In conclusion, films have had a significant influence on the development of many societies.

However, it is the lens through which society changes. Because of their continued advancement, India and Nigeria have continued to watch European films.

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